

ISic3034

I.Sicily inscription 3034

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Heraea

Place of origin (modern)

Ragusa

Provenance

Nunziata Vecchia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332353

1. Θόαϛ

2. [—] XI (?) [—].

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645389

EDCS 71000521

PHI 332353

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 42.0873.1

Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 487-492
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